

Enabling new applications for pultruded profiles by processing local and tailored fiber-reinforcements for improved strength and safety of bolted joints

Patch-Pultrusion

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Pultrusion Technology

Process:

- **Continuous process** for manufacturing of FRP
- High degree of **automatization** and **productivity**
- Profiles with constant cross section
- **High fiber volume content and mechanical properties**
- **Low cost** raw materials and plant equipment

Materials:

- Fibers: Glass, Carbon, Aramid
- Resins: Polyester, Vinyl ester, Epoxy, Polyurethane, Phenolic

Applications:

- Construction, Wind energy, Chemical processing
- Automotive, Transport

Load introductions in high-performance pultrusion profiles

Problem:

- Pultruded profiles offer excellent **axial strength and stiffness**
- **High potential** for applications in links, rods or struts
- Mainly **unidirectional oriented fibers**, constant cross-section, invariable lay-up/fiber orientation
- **Difficult load introduction** in pultruded profiles

Solution:

- Locally adapted reinforcement textiles
- Tailored textiles for high-performance load introductions **without decrease in axial stiffness**

Conventional and local reinforced profiles

Conventional pultrusion profile

Locally reinforced profile

Lay-up of conventional pultrusion profiles:

- Predominantly **unidirectional reinforcing fibers**
- Multiaxial reinforcements (mats/NCF/fabrics)
- Profile thickness needs to be increased over total profile length
- **Oversizing** in most areas of the profiles

Locally reinforced pultrusion profiles:

- Locally integrated fiber-reinforcements
- Locally increased fiber volume content
- **Decrease of profile thickness**
- **Decrease of material input**

Tailored Fiber Placement (TFP) Process

- Placement of rovings in nearly any two-dimensional paths
- ➔ Excellent technology for load-adapted fiber-preforms
- Parallel-stitching for higher cost-efficiency
- Roll-to-roll variant for fiber-placement on continuous carrier tape

Principle of TFP Process

D. Rapping; G. Tandon, 2021

Roll-to-roll TFP process

TFP multi-head machine

tfp-tech.de

TFP-preform

Continuous carrier tape

„Patch-Pultrusion“ Process

Mechanical properties

Pin-bearing tensile strength of 45x5 GFRP profiles

Pin-bearing strength tensile test (adapted from DIN EN 6037)

Ca. +13% local reinforcement of the total fiber volume content

Sample size:
160 x 45 x 5 mm (D10)

Fibre volume content:

UD-profile: 62%
Local reinforcement area: 70%

Material:

9600 tex/1200 tex ECR glass fiber
EP-Anhydrid resin

Mechanical properties

Pin-bearing tensile strength of 45x5 CFRP profiles

Pin-bearing strength tensile test (adapted from DIN EN 6037)

Ca. +15% local reinforcement of the total fiber volume content

Sample size:
160 x 45 x 5 mm (D10)

Fibre volume content:
UD-profile: 61%
Local reinforcement area: 70%

Material:
3700 tex/800 tex carbon fiber
EP-Anhydrid resin

Transfer to more efficient textile manufacturing process

- **Cost reduction** by the use of more efficient textile manufacturing processes
 - Crochet gallon technology offers **local adjustability of fiber orientations**
 - Crochet gallon machine = Warp knitting with variable weft insertion system
- Creation of patterns for **local load introductions** possible

Examples of Crochet gallon textiles:

Gustav Gerster GmbH & Co. KG

Transfer of TFP preform to Crochet gallon textile:

Sample size:
160 x 25 x 4 mm (D6)

Pin-bearing strength tensile test (adapted from DIN EN 6037)

Ca. **+8% local reinforcement** of the total fiber volume content

Fibre volume content:

UD-profile: 63%
Reinforced profile: 69%

Material:

9600 tex ECR glass fiber (UD)
EP-Anhydrid resin

New opportunities:

- Locally reinforced profiles can efficiently **increase bearing strength**
- **High axial- and bending-stiffness** maintained due to mainly 0° reinforced profile
- **Saving of material** expected for mainly compression/tension loaded parts
- **Cost savings** expected especially for carbon fiber reinforced profiles

Outlook:

- Investigation of possible applications
- Transfer to serial production
- Investigation of a possible follow-up project
- Transfer to other process variants

Thanks a lot for your attention!

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Appendix:

- Introduction: Faserinstitut Bremen e.V. (FIBRE Institute)
- Pultrusion activities of the FIBRE Institute
- Additional material characteristics

History:

1969: Foundation from laboratory of Bremen Cotton Exchange

1987: Cooperation with the University of Bremen

- Legally independent, 90% financed by projects and services, 10% by the country of Bremen
- Basic research and applied research activities

Areas of competence:

- Fiber and Material development
- Measurement Systems and Monitoring
- Composite Design and Manufacturing Technologies
- Modelling and Simulation

FIBRE office at the university

Bremen Cotton Exchange

New FIBRE office (EcoMaT)

Pilot plant equipment at EcoMaT

Process Monitoring and Quality Assurance

Inline Microwave Testing

Inline Ultrasonic Testing

Inline Laser-Scanner

Ultrasonic signal

Surface scan (Laser-Scanner)

Process Modeling and Simulation

Example:

Problem: Incomplete curing of profile after start-up due to transient effects of the process

Approach: Process simulation of heat transfer and curing (using 1/4 model in Abaqus)

Before:

After:

- Moving gel zone after 20 min
- Insufficient curing
- Bad profile quality

- Constant gel zone
- Complete curing
- Better quality

Failure behavior and supplementary tests

Failure behaviour at pin-bearing tension

Property	Reference	+/- 45°	+/- 45° (extended)	Loop	Loop (extended)
Compression test Yield bearing strength (in MPa) Standard deviation	469 34.8	446 38.9	426 44.1	469 26.3	408 51
Compression test Ultimate bearing strength (in MPa) Standard deviation	469 34.8	452 40.5	436 27.3	469 26.3	411 47.4
Tension test Open-Hole tensile strength (in MPa) Standard deviation	597 17.8	Not tested -	650 13.9	Not tested -	Not tested -

Open-Hole Tensile Test

Open-Hole Test Specimen before (top) and after failure (bottom)

Cyclic bearing strength (according to DIN 50100)

Test setup (left) and failed specimen (right)